

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

**Effect of a intermittent calorie-restricted diet on type 2 diabetes remission: A randomized
controlled trial**

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Table of contents	Pages
Table S1.....	3
Table S2.....	7
Supplementary approach.....	9
CONSORT 2010 checklist.....	11

Food Items	Frequency of Food Intake									Amount
	Times/Month			Times/Week			Times/Day			Servings per Time
	never	≤1	2-3	1-2	3-4	5-6	1	2-3	4-6	0~7 *
	Approximately _____ % sautéed or stir fried (0)0 (1)1~20 (2)21~40 (3)41~61 (4)61~80 (5)81~100									
26. Percentage of staples cooked in oil (sautéed or stir fried)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
27. Bread and bun (e.g., white bread slice, soft roll, croissant, sweet bun, red bean bun) 1 serving = 2 slices of white bread, one soft roll, two croissants, one sweet bun, one red bean bun	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
28. Root vegetables (e.g., sweet potatoes, potatoes, taro, water caltrop, lotus root, Chinese yam) 1 serving = about 4 wedges or a half Chinese rice bowl	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
29. Low-nitrogen staple foods (e.g., bean noodles, pearl sago/tapioca, tapioca starch products)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
30. Starchy/thickened soup and foods using a starch thickeners (e.g., porridge, soup thickened with corn starch or tapioca flour)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
31. Cakes and cookies (e.g., sponge cakes, pineapple jam cookies, walnut cookie, other cookies cookies)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
32. Seeds and nuts (e.g., peanuts, pumpkin seeds, pistachios, almonds, walnuts, cashews, pine nuts, sesame seeds)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
33. Eating outside (a restaurant, takeaway)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
34. Use of sugar substitute (e.g., Zero Coke and other 0 calories soft drinks, sugar-free candy or chewing gum, sorbitol, oligo-fructose)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
35. Low calorie desserts and snacks (e.g., konjac, gelatin, white fungus, agar dessert, seaweed nori, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
36. Hot foods and liquids served using styrofoam or plastic cups	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
37. Hot foods packaged using plastic bags	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
38. Hot food served on disposable dishes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
39. Handmade drinks (e.g., fruit juices, teas, sometime with gelatinous candies added)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
40. Cup size of handmade drinks 1 serving = one cup	<input type="checkbox"/> Do not eat <input type="checkbox"/> 360 c.c (small) <input type="checkbox"/> 500 c.c (medium) <input type="checkbox"/> 750 c.c (large) <input type="checkbox"/> 1000 c.c (extra large)									
41. Sweetness level of handmade drinks	<input type="checkbox"/> Sugar-free <input type="checkbox"/> Quarter sugar <input type="checkbox"/> Half sugar <input type="checkbox"/> Less sugar <input type="checkbox"/> Regular sugar									

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	Times/Month			Times/Week			Times/Day			Servings per Time
	never	≤1	2-3	1-2	3-4	5-6	1	2-3	4-6	0~7 *
42.Sauces (e.g., sweet-chili pepper sauce, soy sauce, chili pepper sauce, thick broad-bean sauce, BB sauce)	<input type="checkbox"/>									
43.Fermented soy processed products (e.g., vegetarian ham, stinky tofu, jujube, and other vegetarian meats)	<input type="checkbox"/>									
44.Fermented foods (e.g., fermented bean curd, fermented soya beans, miso, natrium bean)	<input type="checkbox"/>									
Chinese Medical Nutrition Therapy (CMNT) diet										
45. Compound Nutrient Rice (<i>Ganoderma lucidum</i> , oats, mulberry leaves, <i>Poria cocos</i> , and <i>Siraitia grosvenorii</i> etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>									
46. Solid Beverage (pumpkin seed oil, tea polyphenol etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>									
47.Nutritional Biscuits (wheat, Phaseolus vulgaris Linn, quinoa etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>									
48.Vegetable Porridge (pumpkin, pumpkin seed oil, tea polyphenol etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>									
49.Multivitamin and Mineral Tablets	<input type="checkbox"/>									
*Answer how many servings (0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7) consumed per time.										

Supplementary Table 2. Kilocalorie intake at baseline, 3 months intervention and 12 months follow-up.

	Groups	Dietary regimen	Kilocalories	Kilojoules	<i>p</i> values
Baseline	CMNT group		2187 (556)	9152.6 (2326.9)	0.91
	Control group	Dietary Guidelines for Diabetes in China(2017 Edition)	2210 (613)	9248.9 (2565.4)	
1-15 days (6 cycles)	CMNT group 1-5 days (6 cycles)	 calories-restrict days	845 (24)	3536.3 (100.4)	0.73
	CMNT group 6-15 days (6 cycles)		2130 (512)	8914.1 (2142.7)	
12 months follow-up	Control group 1-15 days (6 cycles)	Dietary Guidelines for Diabetes in China(2017 Edition)	2089 (415)	8742.5 (1736.8)	0.66
	CMNT group		2285 (247)	9562.7 (1033.7)	
	Control group	Dietary Guidelines for Diabetes in China(2017 Edition)	2253 (308)	9428.8 (1289.0)	

The China Food Composition Database that incorporates the Chinese Food Composition Table was employed to estimate the energy content of a daily meal. Data are daily means (SD).

Supplementary Approaches

Classification of anti-diabetic agents based on action duration

Action duration	Anti-diabetic agents
Ultra short-acting	Repaglinide; Insulin aspart; Insulin lispro
Short-acting	Acarbose; Glipizide; Rh-insulin
Medium-acting	Gliclazide; Isophane insulin
Long-acting	Glimepiride; Glibenclamide; Protamine zinc insulin
Ultra long-acting	Insulin glargine; Rosiglitazone; Glipidazine-controlled release tablets

Specification for home glucose metre for the self-monitoring of blood glucose

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- 1 Rotate and remove the cap of the blood collection pen.
- 2 Fasten the long end of the blood needle into the needle holder.
- 3 Recap the blood collection pen cap.
- 4 Adjust the length of the needle according to individual's skin thickness.
- 5 Pull the plug at the end of the pen back until you hear the snap.
- 6 Place finger at the blood collection site, press the button to eject the needle to collect blood.
- 7 Insert the test paper and start the machine automatically, a small blood droplet will flicker.
- 8 Align the tip of the test paper to the blood drop and the blood will be sucked automatically.
- 9 Waiting for ten seconds, the screen will appear the results of blood glucose level.

The five-level version of the EuroQol five-dimensional (EQ-5D-5L) questionnaire

1.Mobility

- A. no problems B. a little problems C. some problems D. extreme problems E. can not move around

2.Self-care

- A. no problems B. a little problems C. some problems D. extreme problems E. can not care for myself

3.Usual activities

- A. no problems B. a little problems C. some problems D. extreme problems E. can not move around

4.Pain/discomfort

- A. no problems B. a little problems C. some problems D. extreme problems E. can not cope

5.Anxiety/depression

- A. no problems B. a little problems C. some problems D. extreme problems E. can not cope

A= 4 points, B= 3 points, C= 2 points, D= 1 points, E= 0 points

Please score your health condition with the scale below. 100 stands for the best physical condition, 0 stands for the worst.

CONSORT 2010 checklist of information to include when reporting a randomised trial*

Section/Topic	Item No	Checklist item	Reported on page No
Title and abstract			
	1a	Identification as a randomised trial in the title	1
	1b	Structured summary of trial design, methods, results, and conclusions (for specific guidance see CONSORT for abstracts)	3-4
Introduction			
Background and objectives	2a	Scientific background and explanation of rationale	4-6
	2b	Specific objectives or hypotheses	5-6
Methods			
Trial design	3a	Description of trial design (such as parallel, factorial) including allocation ratio	6
	3b	Important changes to methods after trial commencement (such as eligibility criteria), with reasons	7
Participants	4a	Eligibility criteria for participants	7
	4b	Settings and locations where the data were collected	6
Interventions	5	The interventions for each group with sufficient details to allow replication, including how and when they were actually administered	8-10
Outcomes	6a	Completely defined pre-specified primary and secondary outcome measures, including how and when they were assessed	11-12
	6b	Any changes to trial outcomes after the trial commenced, with reasons	12
Sample size	7a	How sample size was determined	12
	7b	When applicable, explanation of any interim analyses and stopping guidelines	13
Randomisation:			
Sequence generation	8a	Method used to generate the random allocation sequence	8
	8b	Type of randomisation; details of any restriction (such as blocking and block size)	8
Allocation concealment mechanism	9	Mechanism used to implement the random allocation sequence (such as sequentially numbered containers), describing any steps taken to conceal the sequence until interventions were assigned	8
Implementation	10	Who generated the random allocation sequence, who enrolled participants, and who assigned participants to interventions	8
Blinding	11a	If done, who was blinded after assignment to interventions (for example, participants, care providers, those assessing outcomes) and how	8
	11b	If relevant, description of the similarity of interventions	
Statistical methods	12a	Statistical methods used to compare groups for primary and secondary outcomes	13
	12b	Methods for additional analyses, such as subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses	13

Results

Participant flow (a diagram is strongly recommended)	13a	For each group, the numbers of participants who were randomly assigned, received intended treatment, and were analysed for the primary outcome	14
	13b	For each group, losses and exclusions after randomisation, together with reasons	14
Recruitment	14a	Dates defining the periods of recruitment and follow-up	14
	14b	Why the trial ended or was stopped	14
Baseline data	15	A table showing baseline demographic and clinical characteristics for each group	14
Numbers analysed	16	For each group, number of participants (denominator) included in each analysis and whether the analysis was by original assigned groups	14
Outcomes and estimation	17a	For each primary and secondary outcome, results for each group, and the estimated effect size and its precision (such as 95% confidence interval)	16
	17b	For binary outcomes, presentation of both absolute and relative effect sizes is recommended	16
Ancillary analyses	18	Results of any other analyses performed, including subgroup analyses and adjusted analyses, distinguishing pre-specified from exploratory	15-17
Harms	19	All important harms or unintended effects in each group (for specific guidance see CONSORT for harms)	14
Discussion			
Limitations	20	Trial limitations, addressing sources of potential bias, imprecision, and, if relevant, multiplicity of analyses	21
Generalisability	21	Generalisability (external validity, applicability) of the trial findings	18-20
Interpretation	22	Interpretation consistent with results, balancing benefits and harms, and considering other relevant evidence	19-21
Other information			
Registration	23	Registration number and name of trial registry	2
Protocol	24	Where the full trial protocol can be accessed, if available	upload to http://www.chictr.org.cn/
Funding	25	Sources of funding and other support (such as supply of drugs), role of funders	22